

A Study on Influence of School Environment on Adolescent Students in Relation to Their Learning Difficulties and Academic Anxiety with Special Reference to Gender and Type of School

Perweez Ahmad Najar

Former M.phil Scholar, Department of Education, R.N.T University Bhopal (M.P)

Email Id: 0126perweez@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research was to identify the factors, such as gender and school type, that contribute to learning disabilities and academic anxiety among adolescents in relation to their school environment. The investigation was conducted using the descriptive research method. Eighth, ninth, and tenth graders representing two types of school administrations, two sexual orientations, and two guiding mechanisms made up the 480-person sample used in this research. In this investigation, the researchers employed the School Learning Environment Questionnaire (SLEQ). The findings showed that when it comes to academic anxiety, there is no discernible gender gap among high school pupils. In addition, the results showed that there is no significant relationship between the school learning environment and the academic achievement of co-educational secondary school students. Moreover, there is no significant relationship between the school learning environment and the academic achievement of co-educational secondary school students with regard to the type of school, the medium of instruction, or any other factor. No significant relationship exists between the gender of coed secondary school students, the school learning environment, the home learning environment, and academic achievement. Similarly, there is no significant relationship between the various components of the school learning environment in aided and unaided schools.

Key Words: School Environment, Academic Anxiety, Gender, Family, School

Introduction

A person blossoms into their full potential through education, much like a flower that releases its aroma into the air. The goal of education should be to help each student develop into an independent thinker and responsible citizen by exposing them to new ideas and concepts and helping them adapt to the dynamic society in which they live. Consequently, a person's readiness to successfully navigate life is the overarching goal of education. An individual should be able to triumph over life's challenges and setbacks with the help of an education. The goals and scope of education are evolving to accommodate the complexity and technical advantages of contemporary society. As time goes on, global competition heats up. Increasing one's standing in society is now dependent on one's level of performance. All parents want for their children is for them to reach

the highest levels of success in whatever they do. The educational system as a whole, including students, instructors, and schools, was under a great deal of stress due to this expectation of exceptional performance. Even though there are many other desired results from the educational system, it seems that the entire system is based on students' academic performance. A person's anxiety may manifest as either a trait or a state. A person's trait anxiety is an innate quality that does not change over time. Exams, accidents, punishments, and other transient environmental conditions might trigger a state of worry. Academic anxiety is a type of state anxiety that refers to the immediate threat that academic institutions, instructors, and particular disciplines (such as mathematics, science, language, etc.) pose.

What makes a school unique is its atmosphere, which is also known as the school environment or school climate. Students' level of certainty will be affected by how they feel about school. Many things can wreak havoc on a school's environment, including its safety measures, rules, and disciplinary practices. In a nutshell, a school is defined by its buildings, classrooms, health services provided by the school, and rules and procedures regarding discipline. In doing so, it prepares the way for the extraneous influences on students. Student results are significantly impacted by educational environments that provide support. A lifelong journey of experiencing and redacting or non-revising events is what education can be, says Dewey (1926). It is the culmination of all those abilities in a person that enables him to control his own possibilities. The physical, social, cultural, and psychological environments all have a role in shaping an individual's growth and development, which begins in the female reproductive organ of the mother. It is crucial for a child's successful learning that they are in an appropriate and sufficient environment, with the home and school both providing the essential input for developing competence. Here, the child's environment—the curriculum, the teaching methods, and the relationships he forms—is having a distinct impact on his performance since he spends so much time there.

Need and importance of the Study

One of the things that makes people act the way they do is anxiety. The fulfilment of other wants or motives may clash with the emergence of an inward reaction or conduct. The concept of anxiety has become a valuable tool in the field of psychology, used to explain a variety of psychological issues. There is a noticeable economic gap in our culture, as is typical in emerging nations. They live differently based on their income levels; some are wealthy, some are destitute. Better educational opportunities for their children are the goal of all parents. Children whose families cannot afford the high costs of private education often attend public schools instead. The majority of India's private schools outperform their public counterparts. Students' sense of self, their level of academic success, and their level of academic anxiety are all impacted by this variation. This line of reasoning inspired the researcher to conduct the current study. A child's academic success ranks high among their life's priorities. It is more critical to learn what makes a difference in kids' academic performance. The primary elements include children's ability, the kind of school they attend, and the level of parental encouragement of student participation in their community. It is striking that the focus in India is on students' academic performance rather than on reducing their

academic anxiety, which is a necessary condition for their academic success. Consequently, the researcher saw a pressing necessity for this type of study because of its practical and immediate relevance. This was the rationale behind the study's inception.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“A Study on Influence of school environment on adolescent students in relation to their learning difficulties and academic anxiety with special reference to gender and type of school”

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the present study are as follows:

1. To study the relationship between school learning environment and academic achievement of co-educational secondary school students.
2. To study the relationship in school learning environment and achievement of coeducational secondary school students with respect to type of school.
3. To study the relationship in school learning environment, and academic achievement of coeducational secondary school students with respect medium of instruction.
4. To study the relationship among various components of School Learning Environment between Gender.
5. To study the relationship among various components of School Learning Environment between Aided and Unaided Type of Schools.

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between school learning environment and academic achievement of coeducational secondary school students.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship in school learning environment, and academic achievement of coeducational secondary school students with respect to type of school.

H₀3: There is no significant relationship in school learning environment, and academic achievement of co-educational secondary school students with respect to medium of instruction.

H₀4: There is no significant relationship in school learning environment, home learning environment and academic attainment of co-educational secondary school students with respect to gender.

H₀5: There is no significant relationship among various components of school learning environment between aided and unaided type of schools.

Operational Definitions of the Terms

Learning Environment: In this study School learning environment refers to the summated score measured by a self-constructed questionnaire on parameters viz promotion of co-curricular activities, physical facilities in school, forbidding punishment and bullying, parental participation, promoting equal opportunities, cooperation and involvement of students, teacher student interaction, personal and professional qualification of teacher, method of teaching and teaching material and socio emotional climate of school.

Academic Achievement: In this study academic achievement refers to the marks of students in their previous year examination.

Co-Educational Secondary School Students: Co-educational secondary school refers to the school where both boys and girls are educated together. In the present study coeducational secondary school students are those who are enrolled in 6th, 7th, and 8th.

Delimitations

Keeping in mind the time, cost and resources, the study was delimited on the following points-

1. The present study is confined to only Pulwama district.
2. The present study is confined to co-educational secondary schools of pulwama district.
3. The study is confined to study the influence of school learning environment and home learning environment on academic achievements of co-educational secondary school students.
4. It is confined to the students of Class 6th, 7th, and 8th. Under aided and unaided type of management of both media (Hindi and English) of co-educational secondary schools of pulwama district.

METHODOLOGY

Population

The population of the study includes all the students of classes 8th, 9th and 10th studying in aided and unaided co-educational secondary schools of Pulwama district. Both boys and girls from aided and unaided management schools of different localities, belonging to English and Hindi medium are taken into consideration.

Sample

In the present investigation, the sample consisted of 480 students concentrating in eighth, 9th and tenth classes of aided and unaided co-educational secondary schools of Varanasi city.

Sampling Technique

The sample for the examination comprised of 480 understudies studying eighth, ninth and tenth classes. The quantity sampling technique was received in two phases. In the primary stage the separation was made based on sort of the executives of school (helped and independent) and mechanism of guidance (English and Hindi). The sampling unit is school. 08co-instructive auxiliary schools situated in Pulwama area were subjectively chosen. Among them 04 supported and 04 independent schools were chosen, out of which 04 were Hindi medium schools and 04 were English medium schools. In the second phase of separation understudies studying in these schools the two young men and young ladies were chosen. From every layer of 04 schools, 60 understudies studying in eighth, 9th and tenth class were chosen (120 young men +120 young ladies). From each school ten young men and ten young ladies were chosen discretionarily. The sample for the current study was accordingly 480 students studying in eighth, 9th and tenth classes similarly conveyed between two kinds of administrations of schools, two sexual orientations and between two mechanisms of guidance. Subsequently the sample was chosen by a two phase amount sampling strategy

Fig 1: Selection and Distribution of Sample

Tools Used for the Data Collection

For the present study two different tools was used:

1. School Learning Environment Questionnaire(SLEQ)
2. Academic Achievement; to know the Academic Achievement of the students earlier years marks (rate) were gathered from the schools.

Statistical Analysis

In order to arrive at meaningful inferences related to the objectives Mean and Standard Deviation was calculated and Karl Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient analysis was used to measure the relationship between school learning environment, home learning environment and academic achievement of secondary school students.

Data Analysis and Findings

1. **To study the relationship between School Learning Environment and Academic Achievement of Coeducational Secondary School Students.**
 - **H₀1: There is no significant relationship between school learning environment and academic achievement of coeducational secondary school students.**

Table1: Relationship between School Learning Environment and Academic Achievement of Co-educational secondary school students.

S no	Variables	N	r	Table Value	Level of Significance
1.	School Learning Environment and Academic Achievement	480	0.63*	0.09	0.05

Significant at 0.05 level

The results show that co-education secondary school students' academic performance is positively and significantly correlated with their school's learning environment ($r = 0.63$). Thus, at the 0.05 level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀1) that there is a substantial relationship between the school learning environment and the academic achievement of coeducational secondary school pupils. The results suggest that a conducive learning environment in the classroom has a positive effect on students' grades. If the school can provide a welcoming, stimulating, and excellent learning environment, the student is more likely to like tutoring. Institutional learning climates can either inspire or impede students' ability to learn; the former is more likely to occur in stable environments, while the latter is more likely to be unstable. Kendziora, Osher, and Chinen (2008) and Osher et al. (2008) are just two examples of the growing body of literature suggesting that students' perceptions of the school environment impact their academic performance. It is possible to conclude that teachers can achieve better learning outcomes than would be possible with guidance alone if they provide students with support that attends to their social and emotional needs and creates strong social and passionate learning

environments. Social and enthusiastic support can take many forms, including creating a supportive learning environment where students feel safe and supported, implementing social approaches to discipline, providing students with academic and behavioural supports to help them understand and follow school rules, and enhancing the social and emotional competencies of students and teachers to better manage their emotions, relationships, and teamwork. Author: Roberta Ann White (2008) Research by Stewart, Endya B. (2008), Ross, John A. (2007), Ballinger, Douglas (2007), and Hale, J. (1965) has demonstrated a strong correlation between a supportive school climate and academic performance. The results of each of these studies corroborate the study's conclusions.

Figure 1

2. To study the relationship in School Learning Environment, and Academic Achievement of Coeducational Secondary School Students with respect to Type of School.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship in school learning environment, and academic achievement of coeducational secondary school students with respect to type of school.

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Score of School Learning Environment, and Academic Achievement of Coeducational Secondary School Students with respect to Type of School

Sl. no.	Variables	Aided (240)	Unaided (240)	r

		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	School learning environment	125.16	11.36	139.36	10.24	0.12*
2	Academic achievement	69.31	11.27	71.05	12.27	0.15*

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The results showed a statistically significant relationship between the types of schools and students' academic achievement ($r = 0.15$) and school learning environment (0.12) when compared by mean scores (Table 4.4.3). Students at unaided schools had higher mean scores (139.96) on both measures, while students at supported schools had lower scores (125.16 and 69.31, respectively). This suggests that students from independent school gangs have a better school and home-absorbing climate than students from independent schools. With a significance level of 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis H03, which states that coeducational auxiliary school kids' academic achievement is unrelated to the school's or their home's learning climate. The results suggest a positive correlation between school climate and type of school; however, students from independent schools performed better than those from supported schools, and the overall estimate of 'r' shows that this correlation is statistically significant. There is strong evidence that the type of school board—whether it's an administration, private sponsored, or private independent school—has a substantial impact on academic performance. The available empirical evidence suggests that, on average, privately run schools outperform publicly financed ones (Kingdon, 1996; Smith et al., 2005; Tooley and Dixon, 2006). Despite adjustments for student demographics and socioeconomic status, large gaps persist in academic performance between public and private elementary schools in Pakistan's Punjab province, according to a study of rural primary schools. Schools in Orissa and Rajasthan, India, had comparable results (Goyal, 2006a; Goyal, 2006b). Also, some people claim that private and public schools have vastly different test scores, which could mean that both types of schools have good and bad ones (Goyal 2006a, 2006b).

3. To study the relationship in School Learning Environment, and Academic Achievement of Coeducational Secondary School Students with respect to Medium of Instruction.

H03: There is no significant relationship in school learning environment, and academic achievement of coeducational secondary school students with respect to medium of instruction.

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Score of School Learning Environment, Home Learning Environment and Academic Achievement of Coeducational Secondary School Students with respect to Medium of Instruction

Sl no	Variables	Hindi (240)		English (240)		r
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	School learning environment	139.23	11.64	138.29	15.62	0.07
3	Academic achievement	67.89	11.26	74.48	11.35	0.36*

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 3 presents the association between the mean scores of school and academic accomplishment of students in the co-instructive optional school programme, specifically looking at the English and Hindi guiding vehicles. Despite a higher mean score in school learning climate (139.23) for Hindi medium students compared to English medium students (138.29), the table shows that the connection was found to be statistically non-significant. Students whose primary language of instruction was English had a statistically significant correlation with higher academic achievement (67.89) (table supplementary information). Students whose medium of instruction was English had much higher academic success (74.48) than those whose media of instruction was Hindi (67.89). So, if there is a school learning climate and academic achievement of coeducational optional school students is 0.05 degrees of importance, the null hypothesis (H₀) that there is no significant relationship between home learning climate and academic achievement is acknowledged clearly. If there is a home learning climate and academic achievement, the null hypothesis is dismissed. It is reasonable to assume that there is a strong correlation between the environment at home for learning and academic success.

Wille (2006) came to similar conclusions when he examined the correlation between students' English language skills and their optional level academic performance. He discovered a favourable relationship between the two. Iranian undergraduates at Shiraz University were the subjects of an investigation by Shahragerd, Baharloo, and Ali (2011) into the correlation between linguistic competence and academic performance; the researchers found a statistically significant positive correlation. According to Orgunsiji and O (2009), English plays a crucial role as a guiding method in elementary, middle, and high schools in Nigeria.

4. To study the relationship among various components of School Learning Environment between Gender.

H₀4: There is no significant relationship among various components of school learning environment with respect to gender.

Table 4 shows the mean ratings of the school learning environment components for boys and girls attending co-ed secondary schools. Table analysis reveals that only one component—teaching

method—shows a statistically significant relationship between the sexes, with males scoring higher (10.07) than girls (9.63).

At the 0.05 level of significance, the following hypotheses are accepted: that there is a significant relationship among the following school learning environment components with respect to gender: method of teaching; physical facilities in school; prohibition of punishment and bullying; parental involvement; promotion of equal opportunities; student participation; teacher-student interaction; teacher qualification; and the socio-emotional environment of the school. The null hypothesis (H010) is thus rejected with respect to the method of teaching.

Table 4: Comparison of Mean Scores of Components of School Learning Environment of Students by Gender

Sl. No.	Components	Boys (240)		Girls(240)		r
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	Physical facilities in school	10.78	2.3	11.67	2.8	0.04
2	Promotion of co-curricular activities	11.86	2.8	12.36	2.3	0.02
3	Forbidding punishment and bullying	9.75	1.3	10.59	1.3	-1.2
4	Parental participation	15	1.2	15.19	2.2	0.03
5	Promoting equal opportunities	8.34	0.9	8.45	1.5	0.01
6	Student participation	15.7	2.3	16.2	1.9	-1.3
7	Teacher student interaction	13.3	3.1	14.4	1.4	0.03

8	Qualification of teacher	8.57	1.15	9.56	0.8	0.01
9	Method of teaching	10.07	1.4	9.63	1.19	0.45*
10	Socio-emotional environment of school	9.22	1.79	10.1	1.54	0.05
	Total school learning environment	137.7	0.38	138.8	0.3	0.07

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The results suggest that boys in both supported and unsupported schools made far better decisions about instructional strategy than girls. Also, according to what Mishra (2002) said, there was a big difference between how the boys' and girls' perspectives on the study hall atmosphere measured relational relationships, objective direction, and the overall climate. They found that, across the board, young men had a more favourable impression of the classroom environment than young women did. On the other hand, differences in balance, educator-understudy communication, co-activity, inclusion, and study tendencies were not statistically significant. The results of this study showed that the two genders saw their educational environment similarly.

5. To study the relationship among various components of School Learning Environment between Aided and Unaided Type of Schools.

H₀5: There is no significant relationship among various components of school learning environment between aided and unaided type of schools.

Table 5: Comparison of Mean Scores of Components of School Learning Environment between Students of Aided and Unaided Coeducational Secondary School.

Sl. No.	Components	Aided (240)		Unaided (240)		r
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1.						
2.	Physical facilities in school	12.89	2.3	13.5	0.56	0.19*
3.	Promotion of co-curricular activities	11.2	2.4	14.8	0.9	0.02

4.	Forbidding punishment and bullying	9.43	1.3	10.9	1	0.03
5.	Parental participation	16.55	1.16	14.32	1.23	0.01
6.	Promoting equal opportunities	7.7	0.9	9.1	0.87	0.04
7.	Student participation	14.9	1.8	18.2	1.54	0.21*
8.	Teacher student interaction	13.6	2.3	15.4	0.72	0.05
9.	Qualification of teacher	8.59	1.25	9.55	0.65	0.02
10.	Method of teaching	9.22	0.81	11.47	0.6	0.29*
11.	Socio-emotional environment of school	8.24	1.12	11.0	0.8	-1.0
12.	Total school learning environment	136.7	0.64	137.7	0.58	0.11*

Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Together, Table 4.6 and Fig. 4.3 show the average scores of aided and unaided coed secondary school students on many components of the school learning environment. Student participation (0.12), school physical facilities (0.19), and instructional method (0.29) were the only three areas where the results showed a significant value of 'r' for both aided and unaided school students. Unaided school students outperformed their aided school counterparts. At the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis (H04) that there is no significant relationship between different aspects of the school learning environment between aided and unaided types of schools is rejected for three aspects: student participation, school facilities, and method of instruction. However, it is accepted for the following aspects: encouraging extracurricular activities, not punishing or bullying students, encouraging parental involvement, and Results show that students in unaided schools are more invested in school life and that their teachers use more effective methods of instruction, leading to higher standards of learning and better academic performance. between coed secondary school pupils' academic performance ($r = 0.55$) and their home learning environment ($r = 0.58$). The results suggest that students' academic performance is positively associated with both their home and school learning environments, and that these two settings also have a favourable relationship with one another.

Educational Implications

1. Any investigation into education is worthwhile if it leads to useful educational consequences. Given that the auxiliary level serves as a foundation for kids' future placement, the study's major conclusions and findings have crucial implications for parents, teachers, and policymakers in the field of education. Students who choose not to attend compulsory education have their academic performance affected by the school's learning environment, according to the research. So, it's up to the parents and teachers to make sure the optional pupils have a great learning environment.
2. In order to create a better learning environment, teachers and parents should encourage kids and divide up the work. Students' academic performance could improve if this were to become a reality.
3. Thirdly, in order to promote a better learning environment at the optional level, educational policymakers and programme organisers should collaborate on significant ideas.
4. Fourth, there is a positive correlation between supplemental school children's academic performance and measures of home environment, such as protection, guidance, and nurturing. Despite this, there is a negative correlation between control, social segregation, and the difficulty of gaining and losing benefits. As a result, the caretakers should be aware of the raring 196 procedures. In order to help parents create a positive home environment for their children and improve their academic performance, schools and educational policymakers should provide mindfulness projects to parents.
5. The results show that supplemental school pupils' study habits affect their grades. Therefore, it is the responsibility of parents, teachers, school administrators, and policymakers in the field of education to provide opportunities for their children to develop better study habits.
6. Students' sexual orientation has an effect on their academic performance in supplemental school, according to the study. In terms of academic success, motivation to succeed, and inclination to study, young women outperform young men. Youth training at the optional level should thus be the focus of parents, teachers, and policymakers.
7. The study found that, compared to kids in public schools, those in private schools performed better academically. Consequently, it is the responsibility of educators and policymakers to enhance the learning atmosphere in public schools.
8. The results show that kids whose schools use the English medium had higher academic achievement than those whose schools use the urdu medium. Teachers and policymakers should therefore concentrate on making urdu-medium schools better places to learn.

Conclusion

Students' academic performance was significantly related to both their school and home learning environments, according to the current study. The character of the understudy's home and school environments is highly predictive of his or her success or failure. Researchers also discovered that understudies at unaided schools rated their learning environments much higher than those at aided

schools and that there is a positive correlation between students' home learning environments and their academic performance in coeducational auxiliary schools. In terms of the manner of instruction, it was found that students learning Hindi had a higher performance in the classroom than students learning English, but the correlation was found to be insignificant. In addition, pupils whose home learning environment was English rather than Hindi had superior academic accomplishment, suggesting a significant association between the two. Furthermore, it was found that there is a significant relationship between the home and school learning environments of co-ed auxiliary school students and their sexual orientation. Specifically, it was found that young men performed better than young women in the school learning environment. Another finding that disproves the existence of sex differences is the lack of a correlation between sexual orientation and academic performance in the context of a home learning environment. Students in supplementary education programmes, both those receiving financial aid and those receiving no such assistance, showed a statistically significant correlation between their home learning environments, their school learning environments, and their academic achievement. The results demonstrate a positive correlation between the three variables related to the type of school.

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